
CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS OF AUTONOMOUS DRIVING APPROACHES: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Autonomous driving is an application of engineering, data science, and computer science, besides other fields, presenting numerous design choices in system development. This review offers a structured timeline of the three fundamental types of autonomous driving: the traditional modular pipeline, the integrated end-to-end approach, and the recent surge in large transformer-based pre-trained models (including language, vision, multimodal, and vision-language domains). We detail the challenges and limitations that can be found in each methodology and how subsequent approaches have addressed these shortcomings. Furthermore, we provide in-depth analyses for examples of autonomous driving systems leveraging transformer architectures, which have demonstrated state-of-the-art performance and overcome the limitations of earlier methods. The paper concludes with a comparative study of these advanced models, a summary of the most frequently employed datasets and architectures, and a discussion of key trends in the field.

Keywords Robotics · Automation · Artificial intelligence · Computer vision · Natural language

1 Introduction

Recently, autonomous driving has become one of the most important yet complex studies in artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics, where we can interpret an autonomous vehicle as a robot that needs to be in motion while having precise positioning with respect to the road lanes, and other surrounding objects, besides the navigation coordinates and autonomous driving system input readings. We can describe the automation of vehicles in five levels, categorizing the development of the vehicle and its dependency on the human driver from one end at lower levels, and the autonomous driving system on the other at higher levels. From that perspective, an autonomous driving application can take one of three forms as a conclusion from reviewing the literature: simulation, a proof-of-concept scaled-down vehicle, or a real-life full-sized vehicle.

1.1 Background and evolution

The study of autonomous vehicles is being developed for a long time, and at the beginning, it had nothing to do with AI, but starting from the driver without assistance, it has improved to have an optional acceleration and braking control, which was referred to as Adaptive cruise control. And developing to the fifth level of automation, which is the fully autonomous vehicle in which the driver has no tasks at all concerning the vehicle motion, and as the following description for the five levels^{1 2} of automation [1] [2]:

1. **Level 0** (No driving automation): In this level, the driver performs all aspects of the driving task without any autonomous assistance, namely driving conventional automobiles.

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2. **Level 1** (Driver assistance): The automation system provides sustained assistance with either steering or acceleration/braking, and an example of the system is adaptive cruise control [3] and lane-keeping assistance [4]. At this level, the automation system consists mainly of a controller such as a feed-forward controller or a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller [5], which could be designed using for example the Root Locus method [6], and it is most useful for a car operating on a slope by controlling the speed or preventing confusion by keeping the lane during a road turn.
3. **Level 2** (Partial driving automation): An upgrade for the system at level 1 by providing both types of sustained assistance, steering, and acceleration/braking. Examples of automation systems at this level are the Tesla Autopilot ³, Cadillac Super Cruise ⁴, and Ford BlueCruise ⁵. We do not know how the companies are building the systems. Still, from experience in systems and control, we can achieve the goal by implementing two controllers of a similar type to the one used in level 1, for each task and keeping both operational simultaneously.
4. **Level 3** (Conditional driving automation): A system at this level has a big difference from the previous level, where the system performs all aspects of the driving tasks within its Operational Design Domain (ODD) ⁶ [7] [8], with driver intervention expected upon request. Examples of systems at this level are the Audi Traffic Jam Pilot ⁷ and the Mercedes-Benz Drive Pilot ⁸. The system, in this case, has a more complex structure, starting from sensors (LiDARs, Ultra Sonic), in addition to algorithms to process the sensor input and output control signals from the vehicle controllers. The link provided in the endnote shows a video of a demo for the Audi Traffic Jam Pilot ⁹
5. **Level 4** (High Driving Automation): The system at this level performs all aspects of the driving task within its ODD, without expecting driver intervention. Some examples of these systems are Waymo’s Robotaxis ¹⁰ and NAVYA’s Shuttles ¹¹. At this point, the system is intelligent and in one or more parts using AI for perception and extracting information from cameras, LiDARs and other sensors, or for planning and to predict the best trajectory for the vehicle, and the main difference between this system from a system of level 5 is that it is for a specific ODD, and not built for all roads and driving scenarios.
6. **Level 5** (Full driving automation): At this level, the system is built to deliver outstanding performance, surpassing a human driver, where the system performs all aspects of the driving task under all conditions without expecting human driver intervention. An example of this is a concept vehicle without a steering wheel or pedals, like the Tesla Cybercab ¹².

and as shown in the table in appendix A [1], a more detailed description of the automated vehicle functions at each level.

1.2 Approaches

Many technologies have been built to improve the performance of land vehicles’ autonomous driving systems, and there are mainly three approaches [9] [10] [11]:

- Modular pipeline (MP).
- End-to-end (E2E).
- Large Language Models and Multi-modal Language Models (LLM).

Each successive approach in this field has been developed to address the limitations of its predecessors while introducing new enhancements. The following sections will present the challenges faced by each methodology and the solutions proposed by subsequent ones. The primary focus will be on the most recent approach, detailing the specific improvements it achieves. The review will concentrate on recent research papers that utilize Large Language Models (LLMs), Large Vision-Language Models (LVLMs), and Large Multi-modal Models (LMMs). We will examine how these models are proposed as solutions. The research can serve as an overview to guide a researcher’s brainstorming process for a new approach to building a state-of-the-art autonomous driving system. Maybe by using one of the many LLMs developed and can be found in the benchmark websites, such as the LMArena leader board ¹³ and Papers With Code ¹⁴. Or by training and fine-tuning a new transformer model specifically built for this application.

The following sections of this research are Section 2, elaborate on the modular pipeline and end-to-end approaches, Section 3, explains the MP and E2E challenges and the resolutions of the LLM, Section 4, Example systems based on transformer neural networks, Section 5 Analysis for the approaches and comparative study for the models summarized in the examples section, Section 6, Conclusion, and Section 7 suggest research directions to explore in building autonomous driving systems.

After large language models, the modularized end-to-end systems showed exceptional results in autonomous driving while being flexible in building, training, and implementing, where the system consists of several modules, each one of them is built of a separate neural network that can be trained and operated separately, and in combination with the other modules, one example model is UniAD [12] which will be further explained in the examples section, and as will be clarified in the examples section of the research that the large models are sometimes improving a module of the system (e.g. VLM-AD [13]) or substituting it (e.g. BEVFusion [14]), in other cases combining two or three modules (e.g. LanguageMPC [15] and DriveVLM [16]) but not always substituting and conveying the full system functionality, i.e. sensor-to-control signals (e.g. DriveMLM [17]).

2 Modular pipeline and end-to-end

In this section will review the two classical approaches, the modular pipeline and the end-to-end automated driving systems, where in the later sections, we will discuss the use and implementation of transformer models based on these two approaches.

2.1 Modular pipeline

This is the more traditional approach for creating autonomous driving systems, and it is not preferred today, mainly because of:

- Its complexity of design.
- The separation of each part of the system into distinct software and hardware.

which results in big challenges in optimizing the system and synchronizing every part of it. The modular pipeline approach breaks down the task of the autonomous driving system into four major parts (modules). These modules are further detailed in the following subsections.

2.1.1 Perception module

This module collects, processes, and interprets the vehicle’s surrounding environmental information by leveraging onboard sensors such as LiDAR, camera, and radar to extract as much information as possible about the road and surrounding objects such as other vehicles. Perception is a process that produces large amounts of data in the form of images, videos, point clouds and other formats [18]. The tasks and technologies of the perception module are mainly part of a computer vision system, such as 2D and 3D object detection, segmentation, object tracking, and sensor fusion [9]. Algorithms for these tasks, includes YOLO [19], Faster R-CNN [20], and VoxelNet [21]. In [22], the tasks of the perception module are defined in more detail by introducing three categories:

- Object detection and identification.
- Depth estimation.
- Simultaneous location and mapping (SLAM).

where both the depth estimation and SLAM have three sensor options, the monocular, stereo and RGB-D.

For example [22], a Tesla vehicle uses:

1. A *Wide-angle camera* has a view angle of about 150 degrees, responsible for recognising objects.
2. The *medium-focal length camera* has a view angle of 50 degrees, responsible for recognizing lane lines and close-by objects.
3. *Telephoto cameras* (Long-focus) have a view angle of 35 degrees and recognition distance of 200-250m

Some of the categories of the features extracted from the images are:

- **Edge features:** Canny operator [23], Prewitt operator [24], Sobel operator [25], Laplacian operator [26], and Roberts operator.
- **Appearance features:** edges, contours, textures, dispersion, and topological characteristics.
- **Statistical features:** mean, variance, energy, entropy, autocorrelation coefficient and covariance.
- **Transformation Coefficient Features:** Fourier transformation, Hough transformation, Wavelet transformation, Gabor transformation, Hadamard transformation, and K-L transformation.

- **Other features:** the color type (greyscale, RGB) and color intensity.

Then the information and features from this module are passed to the Prediction module and the other subsequent modules.

2.1.2 Prediction module

The functionalities of this module are based on the real-time information received from the perception module, and they are analyzing the past and current trajectories of the road users, such as pedestrians and other vehicles detected by the sensors, then predict the future short-term and long-term trajectories and behaviors of the road users to understand the future road conditions and ensure safety and stability [10]. Models for prediction tasks have four types according to [27] listed here:

- **Feature encoding:** where the trajectory is taken as sequential data, and many models are suggested for this case, such as RNN, Transformers [28], VectorNet [29] and MTP [30].
- **Interaction modeling:** where a module for the interaction between different vehicles, pedestrians and road elements is modeled, using transformers [31].
- **Prediction head:** where the probability of each trajectory is calculated by one of the previous two types, some of the approaches use RNN [32] or take the prediction as a regression process and use MLP [33], besides other approaches.
- **Generative model:** including [34] and [35].

2.1.3 Planning module

This module is responsible for generating the best path and trajectory from the current location to the target destination, using the vehicle state (Position, speed, acceleration, direction) and environmental information received from the prediction and perception modules [9]. It has two types:

- **Global planning:** which is concerned with finding the best route from the starting point to the destination on the map using algorithms like A* and Dijkstra.
- **Local planning:** which involves real-time adjustments in speed and direction based on the current vehicle situation concerning the surroundings, common methods are RRT and deep learning-based planners.

In [36], the decision planning process was decomposed into four layers. In this subsection will mention three of them, since according to the categorization of this paper, the fourth belongs to the next module, which is the control module. These three layers are:

- **Route planning:** Is done by finding the shortest path on the map from the current position to the destination.
- **Behavioral layer:** Makes instantaneous decisions about the way the vehicle should interact with the surrounding environment, And predicts the intentions and the behavior of the other objects around the vehicle. And that is done by machine learning.
- **Motion planning:** Based on the behavior decided, a trajectory needs to be found for the vehicle. Using, for example, graph search methods.

And the fourth layer is the local feedback control layer, where the controller generates the actuator signal to deliver the trajectory.

2.1.4 Control module

This part of the system takes charge of executing the trajectory and the path received from the planning module, and it takes into account the vehicle dynamics model and environmental conditions to generate a range of control signals, such as acceleration/braking and steering. The more popular controller to use at this step is the Model Predictive Controller (MPC) [37] [38].

2.2 End-to-end

An autonomous driving system that interprets the driving task as a single learning task, by integrating separate components into a unified system, where it takes raw sensor signals as input and produces a plan as output [9]. This type of autonomous driving system provides more safety and reliability compared to the previous one. Besides other advantages [39] for end-to-end:

1. **Simplicity:** the system is simpler than the modular pipeline because it combines perception, prediction and planning in a single model that can be jointly trained.
2. **Optimization:** the possibility to optimize the system towards the ultimate task as a whole, including its intermediate representations.
3. **Shared backbones:** which increases computational efficiency.
4. **Data-driven optimization:** which improves the system by scaling the training resources.

The most popular methods for end-to-end systems are:

2.2.1 Imitation Learning

Refers to *learning by demonstration*, and works by training the end-to-end algorithm to learn the functionality required by imitating the behavior of an expert algorithm [39] or a human driver. This process requires a dataset containing trajectories collected from the expert algorithm while running, where each trajectory consists of a state-action pair, and the goal is for the end-to-end algorithm to learn and reproduce the expert trajectories. Imitation learning has two types:

1. **Behavior cloning:** [40] This works by minimizing the loss as supervised learning over the dataset [41], the most commonly used method is deep learning neural networks, such as the model suggested in [42], which is built of a convolutional neural network that can learn to steer a commercial vehicle on highways and residential roads. This approach has two shortcomings:
 - (a) Covariant shift.
 - (b) Causal confusion.
 which can be tackled using techniques such as data augmentation [43] and data diversification [44] [45].
2. **Inverse Optimal Control (IOC):** [46] Also referred to as *inverse reinforcement learning (IRL)*, in this approach the IOC algorithm learns an unknown reward function from experts demonstrations [39], for example a human is driving a vehicle and trying to optimize some unknown function with their actions, and the algorithm will be learning to behave similarly given the same state or situation on the road by watching the human driver. Approaches of this type include maximum entropy inverse reinforcement learning.

2.2.2 Reinforcement learning

This approach is based on trial-and-error, so building the model is usually in a simulation environment such as CARLA [47] and Waymax [48] and then implemented to a real-size vehicle, while in case of building the model on a real-life vehicle a driver need to be present to take over as a safety measure. This approach requires significantly more data than imitation learning and training time.

Besides that, one method to enhance the efficiency of reinforcement learning algorithms in terms of training time, while achieving similar results, involves a two-stage process: initial training by imitation learning, followed by fine-tuning using reinforcement learning. [49] [39].

Some of the algorithms used in this type are

1. The Actor-Critic network.
2. The Deep Deterministic Policy Gradients.

From [50] can find clear definitions for the steps of building a reinforcement learning system, and as listed:

1. *State space representation definition:* which includes selecting the relevant sensor inputs and vehicle dynamics.
2. *Designing the reinforcement learning architecture:* which will make decisions for the vehicle motion, such as Deep Q-Network, and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [51].
3. *Reward function design:* which guides the reinforcement learning process to follow the safety guidelines and the traffic rules.
4. *Uncertainty estimation and risk awareness:* to enable the model to make risk-aware decisions and account for sensor noise and other errors, using algorithms such as Bayesian neural networks and Monte Carlo Dropout.
5. *Simulation and real-world experiments:* where the model gets trained on realistic scenarios in a simulation environment, for it to then be implemented in a real-world scenario.

In the next section will discuss some of the shortcomings of the two previously mentioned approaches and suggest another that will work as a solution, and improve the autonomous driving system.

3 Modular pipeline and end-to-end challenges and LLM solutions

Some of the challenges that faced the two previous approaches are generalization, interpretability, causal confusion, and robustness¹⁵ [9]. Many research works addresses these challenges and provides improvements for the autonomous driving system capabilities by adding an LLM or a VLM to the system [9] [39] [52] [53] [54]

3.1 Challenges

1. The modularized pipeline approach *only* challenges:
 - Difficulty in integrating the different parts of the system, which mainly consists of four separate parts.
 - Unavoidable gaps between the system modules, in terms of time delay and accuracy of results, which result in bigger problems and a lack of performance going deeper into the system.
2. End-to-end approach *only* [39] challenges:
 - The information channels from one end of the system to the other are very long, which results in a waste of some information and a delay.
 - The network structure is so complex, and that makes it difficult to debug or optimize the system.
 - The information and driving performance of the networks lack the human driver’s common sense.
3. Explainability: means the results, actions and states of the algorithm in both approaches are unpredictable and not understandable by humans in many scenarios [49].
4. Human-vehicle interaction: The human experience of interacting with the vehicle and the stability of the self-driving algorithm are lacking a lot of possible improvements.
5. Data scarcity: The recording of road data and creating datasets for autonomous vehicles with the correct type of annotation has not always been an easy process, which makes training models with higher performance more challenging.

3.2 Solutions

Some of the challenges of the modular pipeline have been resolved by the end-to-end approach a long time ago, such as the separation and difficult synchronization between different parts of the system, where an end-to-end system solves the autonomous driving task as a single deliverable.

While the high delay and low accuracy of the system are challenges that still can be enhanced in all approaches, end-to-end also delivers a higher performance than the modular pipeline in overall results.

Some of the solutions that were provided by LLMs, VLMs and MLLMs to the challenges that face the end-to-end approach, in addition to the modular pipeline, are as follows: [52]

1. **Perception:** by demonstrating great performance and delivering tasks such as object referring and tracking, and open-vocabulary traffic environment perception, besides having improved performance in perception when data is scarce by relying on their few-shot learning characteristics [55] [56] [57].
2. **Planning:** In this task, the large models have shown great performance, especially in open-world reasoning, and there are two types of large models [58] [59] [13]:
 - Fine-tuning pre-trained models: where there are many approaches and datasets to use for fine-tuning a large model to improve its performance in autonomous driving, some of the approaches are:
 - (a) Parameter-efficient fine-tuning, such as low-rank adaptation [60] [61] [62].
 - (b) Prompt tuning, such as learnable continuous vectors or soft prompts [63].
 - (c) Instruction tuning [64] [55].
 - (d) Reinforcement learning from human feedback [65].
 - Prompt engineering: Some methods tried to use the full reasoning potential with carefully engineered prompts, for example, using the chain-of-thought method to guide the reasoning process of the large model and get the best possible and accurate result [66].
3. **Question answering:** This use case improves the explainability of the model actions and provides a better human-vehicle-interaction, and understandability for the user, which could result in improved dataset generation and the possibility of optimizing the model and improving the driving experience [67] [17] [57] [68].
4. **Generation:** large models can use their generative ability to create videos for driving scenarios, and caption them, besides generating question-answer pairs or descriptions of driving scenes [69] [70] [71].

4 Example systems

In this section, we will mention a few examples for autonomous driving systems and large models implementations, and discuss their most important improvements and differences in the architecture from the foundation model used in building the system, and each one, as the details mentioned in the corresponding research paper.

The systems will be categorized according to the enhanced functionalities they perform, and as the solutions list above shows, in addition to a few examples of end-to-end systems.

4.1 Perception

This subsection will mention the models, with special focus on their perception parts and architectures.

4.1.1 BEVFusion [14]

This research presents a new sensor fusion approach, demonstrating superior performance in comparison to existing techniques and for that, each one will be briefly explained. Sensor fusion is the process of concatenating the features generated by several types of sensors, such as camera, LiDAR, and radar, into a single format, so it can be easily processed by the system parts that come after the perception module. Traditional sensor fusion approaches are:

- *Point-level fusion*: this is an object-centric approach that usually paints image semantic features onto foreground LiDAR points and performs LiDAR-based detection on the decorated point cloud inputs.
- *Proposal-level fusion*: which is also object-centric and works by creating object-proposals and projecting them to extract Regions of Interest (RoIs), one shortcoming of this approach is that it cannot trivially generalize to other tasks.

BEVFusion delivers a big improvement on these approaches, and it works as follows:

1. Apply modality-specific encoders to extract features.
2. Transform multi-modal features to a unified BEV presentation that preserves both the geometric and semantic information.
3. Apply pre-computation, which associates each point in the camera feature point cloud with a BEV grid.
4. Interval reduction, which aggregates the features within each BEV grid by some symmetric function. and apply a specialized GPU kernel to accelerate the aggregation process.
5. Apply a convolution-based BEV encoder to the unified BEV features.
6. Append a few task-specific heads to support different 3D tasks.

Figure 1: BEVFusion overview

As in the Figure 1, the network is built by using Swin transformer [72] for images and VoxelNet [21] for LiDAR, and applies a Feature Pyramid Network FPN to fuse them. Then, apply grid sampling with bilinear interpolation before each task-specific head to meet the output needs of any application task.

4.1.2 EMMA [55]

Presenting an End-to-end multimodal model for autonomous driving. In which the model directly maps the camera sensor data into outputs, including planner trajectories, detected objects, and road graph elements. The model is built on top of Gemini [73], treating it as a first-class citizen of the system. The inputs to the model are:

- Surrounded-view camera videos, to be processed for the perception tasks:
 1. 3D Object detection.
 2. Road graph estimation.
 3. Scene understanding.
- High-level intent command.
- A set of historical ego status.

The model is trained using the chain-of-thought method, which improves the meta-decisions and critical object identification performance. The main functionalities of EMMA:

- Generalizability.
- Predictive driving.
- Obstacle avoidance.
- Adaptive behaviour.
- Accurate 3D detection.
- Reliable road graph estimation.

4.1.3 CarLLaVA [57]

This paper presents a novel system which has a unique architecture from perception to control. The system uses the vision encoder from the LLaVA-NeXT [74] model, pre-trained on internet-scale vision data. for high-resolution images.

In the next stage, using a VLM, concatenate the features resulting from the vision encoder, then, using an adapter, downsample the feature map, and apply linear projection before generating the embeddings for the features.

The system uses the LLaMA [75] architecture as a decoder. More specifically, the model takes camera images, the next two target points, and the vehicle speed as input and gives an output in the form:

1. Time-conditioned waypoints with a PID controller for longitudinal control.
2. Space-conditioned waypoints with a PID controller for lateral motion.

At training time, the mean squared error loss is used to monitor the waypoint generation optimization. and as in Figure 2 The system includes the following properties and advantages:

- Camera-only input, without expensive labels such as BEV or depth.
- Vision language pre-training, which delivers an improvement on training from scratch.
- High resolution input images, to improve driving quality.
- Reduced training time.
- Semi-disentangled output representation.

This model is using the LLM and VLM as an end-to-end system to take images as input and produce trajectories as output, and needs to be connected to a PID controller. Besides that, this system is built to run on the CARLA simulator [47], and can be upgraded slightly to work on real-life vehicle driving.

4.2 Planning

This subsection will discuss the research papers that present the models built to deliver planning trajectories as output, focusing on what makes each one of them superior and innovative in architecture and functionalities.

4.2.1 GPTDriver [58]

This paper presents a model that represents the planner’s inputs and outputs as language tokens instead of taking images and outputting trajectories like other systems, and it leverages the GPT-3.5 [76] [77] [78] LLM API to generate driving trajectories through a language description of coordinate positions.

Another aspect of the model that demonstrates key improvement in this model implementation is its high interpretability, achieved through a three-step chain-of-thought [79] reasoning strategy:

Figure 2: CarLLaVA architecture

1. The planner identifies the critical objects from the perception results.
2. By analyzing the future motions of these critical objects, the planner should infer when, where, and how this critical object may influence the ego vehicle.
3. Using the insights gained from the previous analyses, the planner draws a high-level driving decision and converts it into a planned trajectory.

Another main difference for this model from the others is that it uses the model API, instead of using the model implementation, and editing the architecture to build a complete autonomous driving system.

4.2.2 MTD-GPT [59]

The model is built to manage multiple driving tasks specifically in unsignalized intersections. It introduces a pipeline to build a model, includes two training processes, a data sampling process, and final model evaluation, in more detail:

1. *Training a group* of single-task reinforcement learning expert models based on PPO algorithm [80].
2. *Sampling data* from the expert models' performance in the environment.
3. Utilizing the mixed multi-task dataset created from stacking the expert samples in *training a GPT-2* [81] model offline.
4. Evaluate the GPT model performance.

which can also be considered as an innovative data generation pipeline.

4.2.3 VLM-AD [13]

This research suggests integrating a VLM, GPT-4o [78], into a modular pipeline system using the knowledge distillation approach [82] to function as the teacher, and that will enhance the features and therefore the trajectory produced by the planning module.

The VLM is used at training time only, and not at inference, and that is because using the LLM or VLM directly to reason is time and resource consuming, as a result of the language representation being difficult to transfer into a control command or a planned trajectory, as in Figure 3 (b)

Figure 3: VLM-AD architecture [13]

The process of training this system starts when the VLM model receives the images from around the vehicle, and provides an annotation for the state of the vehicle, then the VLM model gets prompted with questions to further explain the state and decision and provide more information and reasoning to enrich the understanding of the traditional trajectory model.

In the next step, the auxiliary heads shown in Figure 3 receive the ego information from the traditional trajectory model, and align it with the language instructions from the VLM to get an improved decision. and the network used for the auxiliary heads is a language model such as CLIP [83].

4.2.4 LanguageMPC [15]

This paper implements the LLM GPT [76] [77] [78] to function as the brain of the AD system. Which takes a prompt, and the environment perception information, then uses them to make the high-level decisions and creates a low-level mathematical representation to be input into a MPC [84]. In addition to planning for vehicle driving, it presents a chain-of-thought framework [79] for the driver to have a conversation with the LLM, to improve interoperability of the driving decisions.

Figure 4: LanguageMPC architecture [15]

The model functions as follows: the LLM gather information, reasons, and renders judgments. Then, from left to right branches in the center of Figure 4 (a), the LLM will:

- Identify the vehicles requiring attention in the surrounding environment.
- Evaluate the situation.
- Offer action guidance for the ego vehicle.

And the results from all the processes, the LLM gives attention to each vehicle separately and determines if they pose a conflict or not. And from the attention it creates the *observation matrix*. The *weight matrix* defines a situation (i.e. acceleration and steering) that a vehicle could be in, while the bias, which is shown as the *action bias matrix*, is the value of the steering or acceleration as scalar values.

4.2.5 OccLLaMA [85]

This research paper presents a unified multi-modal vocabulary, for vision, language and action (VLA), to unify the VLA-related tasks, including but not limited to scene understanding, planning and 4D occupancy forecasting. using a model based on LLaMA [75] [86] and a VQVAE-like [87] architecture as a tokenizer while using occupancy mapping as perception.

At training time, after a few steps of processing, to get the point cloud features and aggregate them using a pillar embedding, and employ a Swin Transformer block [72] to obtain the BEV feature map. It uses vector quantization to obtain discrete representations. After quantization, the decoder restores 3D voxel features by stacking a convolution block and an upsampling layer.

For the training process, it utilizes three loss functions similar to [88]:

- Cross-entropy for geometry.
- Lovasz-softmax for semantics.
- Embedding loss for codebook learning.

This system uses the LLM as an end-to-end solution to the autonomous driving problem.

4.2.6 DriveVLM [16]

This research paper presents a model plan for the vehicle motion and provides an explanation by the chain-of-thought process, which has three modules:

- *Scene description*: Linguistically describe the environment and critical objects.
- *Scene analysis*: describes the critical objects and their influence on the ego vehicle.
- *Hierarchical planning*: formulates plans from meta-actions to waypoints.

Figure 5: DriveVLM structure.

As shown in the Figure 5, the model has two parts: DriveVLM and DriveVLM-Dual, where the latter incorporates, in addition to the VLM functions, a 3D-perception module and trajectory planning refinement.

The VLM used is Qwen-VL [89] consists of a vision transformer encoder, an attention-based extractor and an LLM. The scene description module identifies critical objects, which are analyzed in three stages:

- *Static attributes*: describe inherent properties, such as a truck’s cargo which could cause a hazard.
- *Motion states*: describe object dynamics, such as position and speed.
- *Particular behaviors*: describe special actions.

The scene analysis dives into the details of the objects, and then the hierarchical planning module generates the plan.

4.2.7 UniAD [12]

The system is built around prioritizing planning for perception and prediction in the corresponding modules. A key component is the query-based design to connect all nodes of the system; in contrast to the bounding box representation, queries have a larger receptive field to soften the compounding error from upstream predictions.

The system consists of four transformer decoder-based modules for perception and prediction, and one for planning in the end. Queries play the role of connecting the pipeline as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: UniAD pipeline structure [12].

In detail, the different components are as follows:

1. The system inputs the images as a multi-camera image sequence, and **fuses the features** using BEVFormer [14] to have a unified Bird’s-eye-view feature.
2. The **TrackFormer** uses the query to get information from the BEV features, and uses the information in detecting and tracking agents, and devises an Ego-Vehicle query.
3. The **MapFormer**, which is based on Panoptic SegFormer [90] with some changes, takes Map queries (e.g. Agents and maps), in addition to the BEV features, and performs panoptic segmentation on the maps to extract elements such as lanes and dividers.
4. **MotionFormer** captures interactions between agents and maps extracted from the previous modules and forecasts (Predicts) future trajectories for the surrounding agents. It captures three types of interactions using a new attention-based model specifically built for the task:
 - Agent-agent.
 - Agent-map.
 - Agent-goal.
5. **OccFormer** takes the BEV features as query, with agent knowledge and predicts multi-step future occupancy, to avoid the ego-vehicle passing in these occupied locations.
6. The **Planner** utilizes the ego-vehicle query from earlier steps equipped with command embeddings to predict the planning result, and stays away from the occupied regions predicted by OccFormer to avoid collision, and attends the plan query to the BEV features, then encodes the waypoints.

Remarkably, every component of the system is constructed with new, specifically designed models tailored to the required tasks.

This research is one of the most compared when it comes to evaluating new models’ performance, and that is because the structure it is built with enables the evaluation of each task separately when required, and also as part of the full

system, in addition to the possibility of replacing one module of the model to have a new and optimized system, besides other considerations.

4.3 Explainability

This section will discuss the autonomous driving systems with attention to the details of the explainability of their decisions and the architecture of the models used.

4.3.1 Agent Driver [67]

Presents an LLM-based autonomous driving system [58], which introduces:

- A versatile tool library that has four modules:
 - Detection [91].
 - Prediction [92].
 - Occupancy [93].
 - Mapping [94].
- A cognitive memory of common sense contains two sub-memories:
 - Commonsense memory.
 - Experience memory.
- A reasoning engine capable of chain-of-thought reasoning consists of four core components:
 - *Chain-of-thought reasoning*: it helps learning by generating a text output for each object in the environment.
 - *Task planning*: produce high-level driving planning.
 - *Motion planning*: generates a text-based trajectory.
 - *Self-reflection*: it is a collision check and optimization approach.

Figure 7: Interpretability of Agent-Driver [67]

These three components are coordinated by LLMs. The driving process starts when the system takes sensory data, process it with neural networks. The output from the neural networks using a *tool library* gets processed by an LLM

to generate text messages for each driving scenario. The LLM output messages get used as a query for the *cognitive memory* to retrieve every relevant traffic rule or previous experiences. After that, a *reasoning engine* takes the perception and traffic rules as input, and generates a trajectory.

As in Figure 7, the output messages of LLMs from the tool library, cognitive memory, and reasoning engine are recorded during system execution. And because of this, the whole driving decision-making process is interpretable and explainable.

4.3.2 LingoQA [95]

The research introduces a benchmark, to test video question answering and a dataset in addition to a vision language model for autonomous driving.

The model is trained to answer questions about driving scenes in addition to general knowledge. The research paper defines an evaluation metric called *Lingo Judge*, in contrast to the GPT Judge [96], and it implements a truthfulness classifier that delivers a 0.950 Spearman and 0.993 Pearson correlation coefficient.

Figure 8: LingoQA architecture

As shown in Figure 8, the baseline model parts are the image encoder and the one used is CLIP [83], and from that, the features are input into a Q-former initialized from Blip-2 [97], to transform the vision features into language features. and then get inputted into LLaMA-2 [75] model initialized on Vicuna v1.5 7B [98].

4.3.3 DriveMM [99]

The model takes images and videos in addition to a user instruction as input, and gets pretrained using the curriculum learning [100] method. to deliver outputs for three tasks: perception, prediction, and planning.

It adapts LLaVA [101], which has three parts:

- Vision encoder, such as SigLIP [102].
- Projector.
- LLM, such as LLaMA 3.1 [103].

The training process of the system is divided into four steps:

1. Language-image alignment.
2. Single-image pre-training.
3. Multi-capacity pre-training.
4. Driving fine-tuning.

4.4 Data generation

One application for the large vision language models is generating videos and images of driving scenarios, which could be used to create new datasets for training autonomous driving systems or improve and expand existing datasets.

4.4.1 VQA-Diff [70]

The research presents a model that improves the quality of the images generated by diffusion models, by adding fine definitions to the vehicles and generated environment, such as the face features of the pedestrians, the car manufacturers details, and the model of the vehicle running on the street. The system is built of a group of diffusion models and an LLM able to learn from an in-the-wild observation, with zero-shot learning prediction.

The system has three parts:

- *VQA large language model text-to-text [97]*: generates the necessary information about the view.
- *Multi-expert diffusion models [104]*: generate a multi-view structures of the vehicle.
- *Edge-to-image ControlNet [105] [106]*: renders the multi-view structures into photorealistic novel view.

Figure 9: VQA-diff [70] framework

The system works as shown in Figure 9 by:

1. Inputting the LLM [97] response with the subject image into a text-to-image [107] diffusion model.
2. Using the output of the text-to-image diffusion, which is a single image with four scenes of the same vehicle, and it get split to four images with a quarter of the area of the first one, and inputted to four image-to-image diffusion models [104] to generate multi-view images from the same subject.
3. Inputting a prompt, subject image, and 16 views structure condition generated from the group of image-to-image diffusion models into ControlNet [105] [106].
4. Using the output of ControlNet, which is a photorealistic surround view in a downstream task.

4.4.2 GAIA-1 [69]

In this paper, a generative system is reported where the system has three inputs: video, text, and action, that get encoded into a shared space, as shown in Figure 10. GAIA-1 works by partitioning the model into two parts:

- *The world model [108]*: reason about the scene components and dynamics, casts the world modelling as an unsupervised sequence modelling problem. using an autoregressive transformer network.
- *The video diffusion decoder [109]*: translates the latent representations into high-quality representations. It is a 3D U-Net with factorized spatial and temporal attention layers.

The model was built as follows:

1. Tokenize the three inputs each according to a specific criterion. where the image tokenizer has a trade-off between the vocabulary size and the sequence length, and it is done using a discrete image autoencoder on two stages:

Figure 10: GAIA-1 architecture [69]

- (a) Compress the information from low pixels.
- (b) Guides the process towards meaningful representation.

The discrete image autoencoder is a fully convolutional 2D U-Net [110], and the losses used to train it are:

- Image reconstruction loss.
- Quantization loss.
- Inductive bias loss.

And for text, there are two choices: character or word-level tokenization. Besides other criteria. And the action tokenization.

2. The world model is an autoregressive transformer model.
3. Video decoder is a 3D U-Net factorized spatial and temporal attention layers, trained on both images and videos.

4.4.3 GAIA-2 [111]

This research paper is based on GAIA-1 [69] and delivers improvements in performance, where this model gives improved control to the environment and the ego vehicle in comparison to the previous one. GAIA-1 used a discrete latent variable while GAIA-2 uses a continuous latent space.

Figure 11: GAIA-2 video tokenizer [111]

The model has two main parts:

- Video tokenizer as in Figure 11. The video encoder compresses the input videos into a compact continuous latent space for the world model to learn from them, predicting the future latent states. And it is made of a space-time factorized transformer, with an asymmetric encoder-decoder architecture.
- Latent world model: as in the Figure 12, which is a time-space factorized transformer trained using flow matching. and takes the inputs as:
 - Past latents.
 - Actions.
 - Conditioning inputs: which includes dynamic agent properties, camera configurations.

Figure 12: GAIA-2 world model

4.4.4 SimBEV [71]

This research paper presents a generative model and a dataset in the form of Bird’s-Eye-View (BEV), and suggests that BEV perception is interesting for two main reasons:

- Conductive to the fusion of information from different modalities.
- BEV Segmentation offers a concise view of the environment.

The model relies on the CARLA simulator [47] with a custom content library. At the time of generating the dataset, the model runs on CARLA to generate videos of a car’s surrounding view, and offers two types of annotation:

- 3D object bounding boxes.
- BEV ground truth, for models like BEVFusion [14] to be trained on.

It works by randomizing (within some bounds) as many simulation parameters as possible.

4.5 End-to-end

The main achievement of transformer-based models in autonomous driving is end-to-end systems, in which they achieve enhanced control and safety by directly learning complex sensor-to-control mappings.

4.5.1 LMDrive [56]

This model processes and integrates inputs from multi-modal sensor (camera - LiDAR) data with natural language instructions. And the output of the model is control signals for the vehicles.

LMDrive consists of two parts:

- Vision encoder generates visual tokens. The one used is designed differently from CLIP, which is the best way to align vision and language, and it works as follows:
 - Implements a ResNet [112] backbone to extract visual features and, after a few steps of processing, get the point clouds that will be aggregated into Bird’s Eye View (BEV) queries.
 - BEV decoder that will process the visual features into tokens of three types:
 1. BEV tokens.
 2. Waypoint tokens.
 3. Traffic light tokens.
- LLM, uses LLaMA [75], with its associated parts (tokenizer [75], Q-former [97], and adapters) that take the vision tokens and natural language instructions, then generate control commands from them. And as the Figure 13 shows:

Figure 13: LMDrive architecture

The training process of the complete system has two stages:

1. Vision encoder pre-training stage. Training the encoder is in three parts:
 - (a) Object detection.
 - (b) Future waypoint prediction.
 - (c) Traffic light status classification.
2. Instruction fine-tuning stage.

While the LLM weights stay frozen at all stages of the training and inference. From the model details and the Figure 13 can find that the model is implementing the LLM as an end-to-end system.

4.5.2 DriveGPT4 [113]

Presents a multi-modal LLM based on LLaVA [101] capable of processing multi-frame video captured by a front-view camera as input and textual queries.

The output of the model is the prediction of the control signal for the next step, besides a natural language answer to the text query.

Figure 14: DriveGPT4 architecture

DriveGPT4 consists of:

- Video tokenizer: consists of a visual encoder (CLIP) [83] and a projector, converts video frames into text domain tokens.
- LLaMA-2 [75] as LLM in the Figure 14.
- De-tokenizer inspired from RT-2 [114].

The training process for the model is in two stages:

- The pre-training stage focused on video-text alignment, using CC3M and WebVid-2M [115] datasets, where only the projector is trained and the encoder and LLM weights are fixed.
- The mix-finetuning stage which is aimed at training the model for question answering, and the part trained is the LLM alongside the projector.

4.5.3 RAG-Driver [116]

This research presents a generalist model that delivers state-of-the-art performance and exhibits exceptional zero-shot performance by the usage of the Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) [117] method to improve the end-to-end autonomous driving system. The model addresses the following challenges:

1. Explainability.
2. Data scarcity.
3. Expensive training requirements.
4. Forgetting.

The model delivers three outputs:

- Action explanation.
- Action justification.
- Next control signal prediction.

Figure 15: RAGDriver overview

RAG-driver has two main components that interact through a retrieval engine, as in figure 15:

- Unified perception and planning unit, built on MLLM backbone, which is Vicuna 1.5 7B [98].
- Memory unit: built upon a hybrid vector and textual database and the retrieval engine.

4.5.4 DriveMLM [17]

The model presented in this research paper is built to run on simulators like CARLA [47]. And to be easily integrated with modular AD systems, it standardizes the motion states and introduces a motion (behavior) planning module, which takes input from (1) Driving rules, (2) User commands, and (3) Sensors such as a camera and a LiDAR.

Figure 16: Comparison of the DriveMLM system structure with classical approaches [17]

The topology of the framework has three parts:

- *Behavioral planning states alignment*: aligns an LLM with a pre-trained behavior planning module. to be able to use the LLM as a behavior planner.
- *MLLM planner*: consists of a tokenizer to generate tokens from the input and a decoder to generate control signals from the tokens.
- *Data collection strategy*.

As shown in the Figure 16, the tokenizer for the images input used is the Q-Former [97]. For LiDAR data, the Sparse pyramid transformer [118] is used as a feature extractor, which gets input to Q-Former to get embeddings

Notably, this research introduces a data engine that predicts and explains motion decisions and generates annotated datasets.

5 Analysis and discussion

The autonomous driving levels give an abstract view of the different functions, parts and capabilities included in the system. As might be intuitive to system designers, simplicity and inclusion are preferred to complex and split systems.

That leads to the fact that deep learning and AI are the best choice for designing autonomous driving systems, since End-To-End systems includes all the functions of the system in one part, especially in the more popular approaches of behavior cloning and reinforcement learning.

The main issue in the end-to-end approach is the interpretability, and complexity of design, which triggers the thought once to split the system into smaller neural networks and try to find the best balance between the two or three networks in complexity and size of the task, but in this case the data scarcity will be a big drawback, when other than the more conventional inputs and outputs are used.

For that, using an LLM or, more generally, a transformer-based network is the best choice to date, since it can solve the problems of previous approaches or get redesigned for that, and any new design can also be supported with the type and amount of data required using generative models and simulated environments.

Which makes using a transformer-based model the best choice for building an end-to-end system, for replacing a single module in the pipeline, or for improving the performance of a module through, for example knowledge distillation method, as in VLM-AD [13].

Considering the research papers discussed and the models being used in implementing an autonomous driving system, can find that the models of interest are mainly three:

1. LLaVA [74] [101].
2. LLaMA [75] [86] [103].
3. GPT [58] [76] [77] [78].

While there are others, such as Gemini [73] and Vicuna [98], they are not used often by researchers in this field.

Another notice is that the planning module is the most researched and suggested for improvement, but the largest change and the approach that might have the biggest potential for delivering an improved autonomous driving system is the end to end system that is mentioned in the examples LMDrive, DriveGPT4, and RAG-Driver, where they take the perception information as input and produce the control signals as output, and that is because the improvement of the large models is still an actively searched subject, to improve the capabilities of the models while keeping the same size or decreasing it.

The evaluation of the models mentioned mainly uses three sets of metrics: 1) planning metrics, 2) the CARLA Simulator Benchmark Leaderboard metrics, and 3) the interpretability natural language processing (NLP) metrics:

1. Planning:

- *L2-Error*, which is the measurement of each waypoint’s distance in the planned and ground-truth trajectories.
- *Collision rate*, which is computed by placing an ego-vehicle box on each waypoint of the planned trajectory and then checking for collisions with the ground truth bounding boxes of other objects [58].

2. CARLA:

- *Driving Score (DS)*, is the product of the route completion ratio and the infraction score, describing both driving progress and safety [56].
- *Route Completion (RC)*, computes the average percentage of routes completed by an agent.
- *Infraction Score (IS)*, measures the infraction penalty between 0 and 1, including collision and violation of traffic rules [17].

3. NLP:

- *BiLingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU)* [119], computes the n-gram based precision of the candidate sequence compared to the reference sequence.
- *Consensus-based Image Description Evaluation (CIDEr)* [120], based on using Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) to provide a lower weight to terms that are commonly reported in the corpus. [95]
- *Metric for Evaluation of Translation with Explicit Ordering (METEOR)* [121], based on a generalized concept of unigram matching between the machine-produced translation and human-produced reference translations.
- *Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation (ROUGE)* [122]: computes the recall-based n-gram of the candidate sequence compared to the reference sequence.

From Table 1 can have a few observations:

- EMMA is the *best in planning* as shown through the L2 error value, followed by DriveVLM, which reports the Collision Rate in addition to the L2 error.
- On the CARLA metrics for planning and End-to-End systems, the CarLLaVA system shows the *lowest performance*, and that might be because it is built for simulation only, so it needs another round of fine-tuning to be fit for real-life use, besides, it uses a camera-only sensor setup.
- Another notice is that Agent-Driver is not surpassing others in any applications, on planning or CARLA metrics, which makes it *less interesting*, even though the Route Completion is second-best.
- From the other models that was evaluated *on the CARLA benchmark*, DriveMLM is showing the *best metrics*, followed by LMDrive, which has a higher Infraction Score but not as good Route Completion.

Models	Planning		CARLA			NLP			
	L2 ↓	CR ↓	DS ↑	RC ↑	IS ↑	BLEU ↑	CIDEr ↑	METEOR ↑	ROUGE ↑
EMMA [55]	0.29
CarLLaVA [57]	.	.	6.87	18.08	0.41
GPTDriver [58]	0.84	0.44
VLM-AD [13]	0.48	0.23
DriveVLM [16]	0.31	0.10
UniAD [12]	1.03	0.31
Agent Driver [67]	0.74	0.21	57.33	91.37
LingoQA [95]	14.21	59.46	18.4	.
DriveMM [99]	39.11	77.5	.	34.15
LMDrive [56]	.	.	66.5	77.9	0.85
DriveGPT4 [113]	18.32	99.1	.	44.73
RAG-Driver [116]	34.3	260.8	30.7	.
DriveMLM [17]	.	.	76.1	98.1	0.78	46.46	124.91	56.54	.

Table 1: Model evaluation and results. Metrics used are: L2: average L2 error (in meters), CR: Collision Rate (in percentage), DS: Driving Score, RC: Route Completion, IS: Infraction Score, BLEU: BiLingual Evaluation Understudy, CIDEr: Consensus-based Image Description Evaluation, METEOR: Metric for Evaluation of Translation with Explicit ORdering, ROUGE: Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation. and the values in the table are found in the research paper and each according to the application it was built for.

- For the NLP metrics, once again, the DriveMLM system is the best, followed by RAG-Driver, which is reporting an outstanding performance on the CIDEr metric.
- Among all the example systems mentioned, the DriveMLM shows the highest performance in functioning as an explainable End-to-End driving system.

In addition to the mentioned models and architectures, a group of the most popular and used datasets are in Table 2 [9] [49]

Dataset	Task
KITTI [123]	3D & 2D Object Detection, Semantic Segmentation, Object Tracking
Cityscapes [124]	3D & 2D Object Detection, Semantic Segmentation
CityFlow [125]	Object Tracking, Re-Identification
nuScenes [126]	3D & 2D Object Detection, 3D & 2D Semantic Segmentation, Object Tracking, Motion Planning
BDD100K [127]	2D Object Detection, 2D Semantic Segmentation, Object Tracking
Waymo [128]	3D & 2D Object Detection, 2D Semantic Segmentation, Object Tracking
BDD-X [129]	2D Object Detection, 2D Semantic Segmentation, Object Tracking, Action Explanation
NuPrompt [130]	Multiple Object referring and tracking
Talk2BEV [131]	Visual question Answering,
DRAMA [132]	Image Captioning, Visual Question Answering
DeepDrive-X [129]	Global Navigation Satellite system, Text annotation

Table 2: Datasets and their supported tasks

6 Conclusion

The systems that include large language models and large vision models can be a solution for many challenges for the previous approaches, and some of them can deliver performance enhancements to the modular pipeline and end-to-end systems, in addition to possibly replacing them fully or partially.

The LLMs enable the building of a new type of system, which is more inclusive, in contrast to the traditional end-to-end; it does not need a controller after the last step but delivers the controller signal as output after taking the perception information as input.

In addition to that, the LLMs enable data generation, which is a task that was not addressed by the modular pipeline and the classical end-to-end, since video, images, and text datasets are scarce in usual, so generating and simulating driving environments would be a great addition to the autonomous driving industry.

Explainability is another application for large vision and language models that did not exist as part of the other two approaches, it improves the possibility of optimizing the systems further by understanding their behavior and communicating with some of them.

So we can notice that large language models and large vision models can transform the autonomous driving system into a more similar experience to a human driver.

7 Further research

Many methods can be derived from the models and explanations mentioned in this review:

- Visiting again the *knowledge distillation* used in the VLM-AD, where a traditional planning module learned from a VLM, and applying it to, for example, the UniAD system or the DriveMLM model, trying to further improve the results, that is already superior to all the models mentioned, and relevant to mention that the LLM in DriveMLM was aligned with a pre-trained behavior planning module.
- Including audio detection can improve some edge cases, such as detecting horn honking from a far-away fast vehicle, or an emergency response vehicle, and clear the road for them or take them into consideration in future plans, and improve safety.
- Build system using new and more suitable models, namely, Liquid foundation models [133] [134], which take into consideration the vehicle dynamics in addition to other inputs and features.

Besides many other possible methods and studies.

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Notes

¹Description for the five automation levels: https://www.sae.org/standards/content/j3016_202104/

²Further details about autonomous driving basics: <https://medium.com/@samiratra95/autonomous-driving-modular-pipeline-vs-end-to-end-and-llms-642ca7f4ef89>

³Tesla Autopilot: <https://www.tesla.com/support/autopilot>

⁴Cadillac Super Cruise: <https://www.cadillac.com/technology/super-cruise?srsltid=AfmB0oreWh2WLT4WNRXOEYAveVE2Z9cSAsY3-vz0ghbYBXf31VaCFt8Eq>

⁵Ford BlueCruise: <https://www.ford.com/technology/bluecruise/>

⁶ODD: <https://www.sae.org/standards/content/j3259/>

⁷Audi Traffic Jam Pilot: <https://magazine.audi.com.au/article/audi-ai-traffic-jam-pilot>

⁸Mercedes-Benz Drive Pilot: https://www.mercedes-benz.nl/passengercars/technology/drive-pilot.html?srsltid=AfmB0oo8iNXoLpZ8xQRonozBIw8w1Nh2PKpWh5noIshDEtztlwcI9Ip_

⁹Audi Traffic Jam Pilot: https://www.audi-mediacycenter.com/en/videos/video/footage-audi-a8-audi-ai-traffic-jam-pilot-3785?source=post_page-----642ca7f4ef89-----

¹⁰Waymo's Robotaxis: <https://waymo.com/>

¹¹NAVYA's Shuttles: <https://www.navya.tech/en/solutions/moving-people/self-driving-shuttle-for-passenger-transportation/>

¹²Tesla Cybercab: <https://youtu.be/Qfj4urMF8CU>

¹³LMARena LeaderBoard: https://lmarena.ai/?gad_source=1&gad_campaignid=21946979971&gbraid=OAAAAA-d12XMawev6z-UC0jrXVNUD_uIur&gclid=Cj0KQjw_dbABhC5ARIsAAh2Z-SHCGqDXcK6GJD1s56sKbQQ1BXFIZR_iw1DcmpghgNaD_bzEkS07moaAk31EALw_wcB

¹⁴Papers with code: <https://paperswithcode.com/>

¹⁵Further reading about challenges and solutions: https://open.substack.com/pub/samerattrah/p/autonomous-driving-with-llms-vlms?r=2nuo7w&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web&showWelcomeOnShare=false

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A Vehicle functions authority at each automation stage

Function	Level 0 (No automation)	Level 1 (Driving assistant)	Level 2 (Partial automation)	Level 3 (Conditional automation)	Level 4 (High automation)	Level 5 (Full automation)
Steering control	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Acceleration and Deceleration	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Braking	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Lane keeping	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Lane changing	Human driver	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Navigation and Route planning	Human driver	Human driver	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system
Traffic sign and signal recognition	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Object detection and response	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Parking	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Monitoring vehicle system	Human driver	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Emergency response	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Adaptive cruise control	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Environmental perception	Human driver	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication	Human driver	Human driver	Human driver	Automation system	Automation system	Automation system
Driver Monitoring (Semi-autonomous Vehicles)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Human driver	Human driver	Not applicable	Not applicable

Table 3: 15 functions of vehicle automation, that indicate who has authority at each stage of automation [1]